

Foreword

We organize the following contents according to the appearance order of figures and tables in the paper. NPU related data first and GPU's followed. Due to the NPU device properties, noises within 0.5% between two runs of the same case should be ignored for the results reported for our NPU.

NPU

server

Host: 60.207.218.226

Port: 2022

User: wangchengke

Password: 123.com

code repository

```
# root directory
```

```
~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
```

```
# alias
```

```
$HOME_DIR
```

```
# env
```

```
source ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/env.sh
```

scripts of related models

label	model	config	dir path	alias
A	resnet50 v1.5	fp16, batch=16	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/resnet50_v1p5/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_A</code>
	resnet50 v1.5	int8, batch=16	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/resnet50_v1p5/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_A</code>
	resnet50 v2	fp16, batch=16	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/resnet50_v2/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_A_1</code>
	resnet50 v2	int8, batch=16	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/resnet50_v2/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_A_1</code>
B	bert-128	batch=2, seq-num=128	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/bert_128_batch_2/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_B_1</code>
	bert-128	batch=4, seq-num=128	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/bert_128_batch_4/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_B_2</code>
	bert-128	batch=8, seq-num=128	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/bert_128_batch_8/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_B</code>
	bert-128	batch=16, seq-num=128	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/bert_128_batch_16/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_B_3</code>
	bert-256	batch=4, seq-num=256	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/bert_256/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_C</code>
	bert-384	batch=2, seq-num=384	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/bert_large/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_D</code>
	bert-512	batch=2, seq-num=512	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/bert_512/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_E</code>
	d1rm	batch=256	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/d1rm/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_F</code>
	mobilenet v2	batch=32	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/mobilenet_v2/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_G</code>
	vision_transformer	batch=8	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/vision_transformer/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_H</code>
	densenet121	batch=8	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/densenet121/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_I</code>
	conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small	batch=3	<code>\$HOME_DIR/models/conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small/src/</code>	<code>\$MODEL_J</code>

reproduce the data

Table 1

We report the number of cycles in `total_cycles`; which the reviewers can convert into the data `throughput` or `latency` (reported in the paper) using the formulas listed in the table.

```
# initial setup
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
source env.sh
# reproduce every single data item
```

approach	batch size (iter * batch * cluster)	command	cycle	throughput (fps)	latency (ms)
TVM	8 (1 * 2 * 4)	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$round\left(\frac{2}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$	$round\left(\frac{cycle}{1.0E+6}, 2\right)$
	16 (1 * 4 * 4)	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B_2 conda activate py37_tf_1.14_bert_128_4 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$round\left(\frac{4}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$	$round\left(\frac{cycle}{1.0E+6}, 2\right)$

32 (2 * 4 * 4)	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B_2 conda activate py37_tf_1.14_bert_128_4 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>	$round\left(\frac{4}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$	$round\left(\frac{cycle}{1.0E+6}, 2\right) * 2$
64 (4 * 4 * 4)	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B_2 conda activate py37_tf_1.14_bert_128_4 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>	$round\left(\frac{4}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$	$round\left(\frac{cycle}{1.0E+6}, 2\right) * 4$
8 (1 * 2 * 4)	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>	$round\left(\frac{2}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$	$round\left(\frac{cycle}{1.0E+6}, 2\right)$
GraphTurbo	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B_2 conda activate py37_tf_1.14_bert_128_4 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>	$round\left(\frac{4}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$	$round\left(\frac{cycle}{1.0E+6}, 2\right)$

32 (1 * 8 * 4)	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$	$\text{round}\left(\frac{\text{cycle}}{1.0E+6}, 2\right)$
64 (1 * 16 * 4)	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B_3 conda activate py37_tf_1.14_bert_128_16 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 -- batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{16}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$	$\text{round}\left(\frac{\text{cycle}}{1.0E+6}, 2\right)$
64 (2 * 8 * 4)	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$	$\text{round}\left(\frac{\text{cycle}}{1.0E+6}, 2\right) * 2$
crafted code 32 (1 * 8 * 4)	<pre>cd \$HOME_DIR/vendor-crafted/ ./bert_128_fp16.out &> out.log cat out.log grep -a -m1 "mcu_perf_cnt"</pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$	$\text{round}\left(\frac{\text{cycle}}{1.0E+6}, 2\right)$

Table 2

TVM's result in Table 2

We report the number of cycles in `total_cycles`, and the reviewers can convert it to final result `throughput` using the formulas listed in the table.

```
# initial setup
```

```
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
```

```
source env.sh
```

```
# reproduce every single data item
```

label	model	command	cycle	throughput (fps)
A	ResNet-50	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v1p5.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{16}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
B	BERT-128	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
C	BERT-256	<pre>cd \$MODEL_C conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_256.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{4}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

D	BERT-384	<pre> cd \$MODEL_D conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_large.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{2}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
E	BERT-512	<pre> cd \$MODEL_F conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_dlrn.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=1024 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{1024}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
F	DLRM	<pre> cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{32}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
G	MobileNet-v2	<pre> cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
H	Vision_Transformer	<pre> cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

```
I      DenseNet      cd $MODEL_I
      conda activate py37_tf_1.14
      python test_densenet121.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --
      generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=8 &>
      out.log
      cat out.log | grep "total_cycles"
      cd $MODEL_J
      conda activate py37_tf_1.14
      python test_conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --
      test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --
      schedule_level=0 --batch=3 &> out.log
      cat out.log | grep "total_cycles"
```

$$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$$

$$\text{round}\left(\frac{3}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$$

Figure 14

Astitch's result in Figure 14

We report the number of cycles in `total_cycles`, and the reviewers can convert it to final result `throughput` using the formulas listed in the table.

```
# initial setup
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
source env.sh
export OFF=on
export SCOPE="shared_LLB"
# reproduce every single data item
```

label	model	command	cycle	throughput (fps)
A	ResNet-50	cd \$MODEL_A conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v1p5.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"		$round\left(\frac{16}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
B	BERT-128	cd \$MODEL_B conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"		$round\left(\frac{8}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

C	BERT-256	<pre> cd \$MODEL_C conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_256.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_D conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_large.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{4}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
D	BERT-384	<pre> cd \$MODEL_D conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_large.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{2}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
E	BERT-512	<pre> cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{2}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
F	DLRM	<pre> cd \$MODEL_F conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_dlrn.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=1024 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{1024}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
G	MobileNet-v2	<pre> cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{32}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

H	Vision_Transformer	<pre> cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_I conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_densenet121.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_J conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule -- schedule_level=2 --batch=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
I	DenseNet	<pre> cd \$MODEL_I conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_densenet121.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_J conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule -- schedule_level=2 --batch=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
J	Conformer	<pre> cd \$MODEL_J conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule -- schedule_level=2 --batch=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{3}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

vendor-crafted implementation's result in Figure 14

We report the number of cycles in `total_cycles`, and the reviewers can convert it to final result `throughput` using the formulas listed in the table.

```
# initial setup
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
source env.sh
cd vendor-crafted/
# reproduce every single data item
```

label	model	command	cycle	throughput (fps)
A	ResNet-50	<code>./resnet50v1p5_fp16.out &> out.log</code> <code>cat out.log grep -a -m1 "mcu_perf_cnt"</code>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{16}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
B	BERT-128	<code>./bert_128_fp16.out &> out.log</code> <code>cat out.log grep -a -m1 "mcu_perf_cnt"</code>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
C	BERT-256	<code>./bert_256_fp16.out &> out.log</code> <code>cat out.log grep -a "mcu_perf_cnt" tail -1</code>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{4}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
D	BERT-384	<code>./bert_384_fp16.out &> out.log</code> <code>cat out.log grep -a "mcu_perf_cnt" tail -1</code>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{2}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
E	BERT-512	<code>./bert_512_fp16.out &> out.log</code> <code>cat out.log grep -a "mcu_perf_cnt" tail -1</code>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{2}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
F	DLRM	-		
G	MobileNet-v2	<code>./mobilenetv2.out &> out.log</code> <code>cat out.log grep -a "mcu_perf_cnt" tail -1</code>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{32}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
H	Vision_Transformer	-		
I	DenseNet	-		
J	Conformer	-		

GraphTurbo's result in Figure 14

We report the number of cycles in `total_cycles`, and the reviewers can convert it to final result `throughput` using the formulas listed in the table.

```
# initial setup
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
source env.sh
# reproduce every single data item
```

label	model	command	cycle	throughput (fps)
A	ResNet-50	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v1p5.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$round\left(\frac{16}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
B	BERT-128	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$round\left(\frac{8}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
C	BERT-256	<pre>cd \$MODEL_C conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_256.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$round\left(\frac{4}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

D	BERT-384	<pre> cd \$MODEL_D conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_large.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{2}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
E	BERT-512	<pre> cd \$MODEL_F conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_dlrn.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=1024 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{1024}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
F	DLRM	<pre> cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{32}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
G	MobileNet-v2	<pre> cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
H	Vision_Transformer		

I	DenseNet	<pre>cd \$MODEL_I conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_densenet121.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_J conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule -- schedule_level=3 --batch=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
J	Conformer		$\text{round}\left(\frac{3}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

Figure 15

"stay in LLB" in Figure 15

We report the number of cycles in `total_cycles`, and the reviewers can convert it to final result `throughput` using the formulas listed in the table.

```
# initial setup
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
source env.sh
export OFF=on
# reproduce every single data item
```

label	model	command	cycle	throughput (fps)
A	ResNet-50	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v1p5.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$round\left(\frac{16}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
B	BERT-128	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$round\left(\frac{8}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
C	BERT-256	<pre>cd \$MODEL_C conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_256.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$round\left(\frac{4}{cycle/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

D	BERT-384	<pre> cd \$MODEL_D conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_large.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{2}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
E	BERT-512	<pre> cd \$MODEL_F conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_dlrn.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 --batch=1024 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{1024}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
F	DLRM	<pre> cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{32}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
G	MobileNet-v2	<pre> cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
H	Vision_Transformer		

```
I      DenseNet      cd $MODEL_I
      conda activate py37_tf_1.14
      python test_densenet121.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --
      generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=1 --batch=8 &>
      out.log
      cat out.log | grep "total_cycles"
      cd $MODEL_J
      conda activate py37_tf_1.14
      python test_conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --
      test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --
      schedule_level=1 --batch=3 &> out.log
      cat out.log | grep "total_cycles"
```

$$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$$

$$\text{round}\left(\frac{3}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$$

"stay in L1" in Figure 15

We report the number of cycles in `total_cycles`, and the reviewers can convert it to final result `throughput` using the formulas listed in the table.

```
# initial setup
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
source env.sh
export OFF=on
# reproduce every single data item
```

label	model	command	cycle	throughput (fps)
A	ResNet-50	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v1p5.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{16}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
B	BERT-128	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
C	BERT-256	<pre>cd \$MODEL_C conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_256.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{4}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

D	BERT-384	<pre> cd \$MODEL_D conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_large.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{2}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
E	BERT-512	<pre> cd \$MODEL_F conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_dlrn.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=1024 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{1024}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
F	DLRM	<pre> cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{32}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
G	MobileNet-v2	<pre> cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
H	Vision_Transformer		

```
I      DenseNet      cd $MODEL_I
      conda activate py37_tf_1.14
      python test_densenet121.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --
      generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=2 --batch=8 &>
      out.log
      cat out.log | grep "total_cycles"
      cd $MODEL_J
      conda activate py37_tf_1.14
      python test_conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --
      test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --
      schedule_level=2 --batch=3 &> out.log
      cat out.log | grep "total_cycles"
```

$$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$$

$$\text{round}\left(\frac{3}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$$

"+ instance ordering" in Figure 15

We report the number of cycles in `total_cycles`, and the reviewers can convert it to final result `throughput` using the formulas listed in the table.

```
# initial setup
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
source env.sh
export OFF=on
# reproduce every single data item
```

label	model	command	cycle	throughput (fps)
A	ResNet-50	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v1p5.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{16}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
B	BERT-128	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
C	BERT-256	<pre>cd \$MODEL_C conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_256.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{4}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

D	BERT-384	<pre> cd \$MODEL_D conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_large.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{2}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
E	BERT-512	<pre> cd \$MODEL_F conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_dlrn.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=1024 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{1024}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
F	DLRM	<pre> cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{32}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
G	MobileNet-v2	<pre> cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
H	Vision_Transformer		

I	DenseNet	<pre>cd \$MODEL_I conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_densenet121.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_J conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule -- schedule_level=3 --batch=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
J	Conformer		$\text{round}\left(\frac{3}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

"+ instruction scheduling" in Figure 15

We report the number of cycles in `total_cycles`, and the reviewers can convert it to final result `throughput` using the formulas listed in the table.

```
# initial setup
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
source env.sh
# reproduce every single data item
```

label	model	command	cycle	throughput (fps)
A	ResNet-50	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v1p5.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{16}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
B	BERT-128	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
C	BERT-256	<pre>cd \$MODEL_C conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_256.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles"</pre>		$\text{round}\left(\frac{4}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

D	BERT-384	<pre> cd \$MODEL_D conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_large.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{2}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
E	BERT-512	<pre> cd \$MODEL_F conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_dlrn.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=1024 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{1024}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
F	DLRM	<pre> cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{32}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
G	MobileNet-v2	<pre> cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$
H	Vision_Transformer	<pre> cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep "total_cycles" </pre>	$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$

```
I      DenseNet      cd $MODEL_I
      conda activate py37_tf_1.14
      python test_densenet121.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --
      generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &>
      out.log
      cat out.log | grep "total_cycles"
      cd $MODEL_J
      conda activate py37_tf_1.14
      python test_conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --
      test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --
      schedule_level=3 --batch=3 &> out.log
      cat out.log | grep "total_cycles"
```

$$\text{round}\left(\frac{8}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$$

$$\text{round}\left(\frac{3}{\text{cycle}/1.0E+9}, 0\right) * 4$$

Table 3

"buffer scopes" in Table 3

The final result is `kernel scopes`.

```
# initial setup
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
source env.sh
export KERNEL=on
# reproduce every single data item
```

	label	model	command	kernel scope num (ddr/lb/11/total)
	A	ResNet-50	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v1p5.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"</pre>	58/0/0/58
TVM	B	BERT-128	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"</pre>	242/0/0/242
	C	BERT-256	<pre>cd \$MODEL_C conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_256.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"</pre>	242/0/0/242

D	BERT-384	cd \$MODEL_D conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_large.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	515/0/0/515
E	BERT-512	cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	242/0/0/242
F	DLRM	cd \$MODEL_F conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_dlrn.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=1024 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	76/0/0/76
G	MobileNet-v2	cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	56/0/0/56
H	Vision_Transformer	cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	214/0/0/214

		<pre> cd \$MODEL_I conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_densenet121.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes" cd \$MODEL_J conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=0 - -batch=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes" </pre>	247/0/0/247
I	DenseNet		
J	Conformer		1054/0/0/1054
A	ResNet-50	<pre> cd \$MODEL_A conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v1p5.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=ManulSchedule --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes" </pre>	1/11/291/303
B	BERT-128	<pre> cd \$MODEL_B conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=ManulSchedule --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes" </pre>	2/0/304/306
C	BERT-256	<pre> cd \$MODEL_C conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_256.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=ManulSchedule --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes" </pre>	2/25/401/428
D	BERT-384	-	-
E	BERT-512	<pre> cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=ManulSchedule --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes" </pre>	2/25/474/501

crafted

		cd \$MODEL_F		
		conda activate py37_tf_1.14		
F	DLRM	python test_dlrn.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=ManualSchedule --batch=1024 &> out.log	1/0/75/76	
		cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"		
		cd \$MODEL_G		
		conda activate py37_tf_1.14		
G	MobileNet-v2	python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=ManualSchedule --batch=32 &> out.log	1/7/619/627	
		cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"		
H	Vision_Transformer	-	-	
I	DenseNet	-	-	
J	Conformer	-	-	
		cd \$MODEL_A		
		conda activate py37_tf_1.14		
A	ResNet-50	python test_resnet50_v1p5.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=16 &> out.log	0/11/284/295	
		cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"		
		cd \$MODEL_B		
		conda activate py37_tf_1.14		
GraphTurbo	B	BERT-128	python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log	1/0/305/306
			cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	
		cd \$MODEL_C		
		conda activate py37_tf_1.14		
		python test_bert_256.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=4 &> out.log	1/110/240/351	
			cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	

D	BERT-384	cd \$MODEL_D conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_large.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	1/75/967/1043
E	BERT-512	cd \$MODEL_E conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_bert_512.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	1/76/337/414
F	DLRM	cd \$MODEL_F conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_dlrn.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=1024 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	0/0/76/76
G	MobileNet-v2	cd \$MODEL_G conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_mobilenet_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=32 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	0/3/608/611
H	Vision_Transformer	cd \$MODEL_H conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_vision_transformer.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"	24/60/340/424

I	DenseNet	<pre>cd \$MODEL_I conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_densenet121.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False -- generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes" cd \$MODEL_J conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_conformer_speech_pt_fp32_small.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False -- test_flag=False --generation=gen1 --schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 - -batch=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 4 "kernel scopes"</pre>	0/3/389/392
J	Conformer		4/813/250/1067

Figure 16

"buffer scopes" in Table 3

We report the numbers of cycles in **theoretical cycles(MME、VME)** and **device cycles(mme_cycles、vme_cycles)**, then take the percentages of both as final results, respectively.

```
# initial setup
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
source env.sh
export THEO_CYCLE=on
# reproduce every single data item
```

model	batch	command	mme	vme
(a) ResNet-50 (FP16)	1	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=1 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"</pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
	2	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"</pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$

4	<pre> cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'" </pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
8	<pre> cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'" </pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
16	<pre> cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'" </pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
(b) ResNet-50 (INT8)	<pre> cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=True --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=1 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'" </pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$

2	<pre> cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=True --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=2 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'" </pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
4	<pre> cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=True --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'" </pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
8	<pre> cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=True --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'" </pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
16	<pre> cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_resnet50_v2.py --rounds=1 --quantize=True --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'" </pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$

		<pre>cd \$MODEL_B_2 conda activate py37_tf_1.14_bert_128_4 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=4 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"</pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
(c) BERT-128	8	<pre>python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=8 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"</pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
	16	<pre>cd \$MODEL_B_3 conda activate py37_tf_1.14_bert_128_16 python test_bert_128.py --rounds=1 --quantize=False --test_flag=False --generation=gen1 -- schedule_mode=AutoSchedule --schedule_level=3 --batch=16 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"</pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$

Figure 17

Utilization VME (left) and Utilization MME (right) in Figure 17

We report the numbers of cycles in `theoretical cycles(MME、VME)` and `device cycles(mme_cycles、vme_cycles)`, then take the percentage of both as final results, respectively.

```
# initial setup
cd ~/tmp/artifact_osdi_23_957/
source env.sh
export THEO_CYCLE=on
# reproduce every single data item
```

stage	command	mme	vme
stage 1	cd \$MODEL_A_1		
	conda activate py37_tf_1.14		
	python test_stages.py --rounds=1 --batch=1 --schedule_level=0 &> out.log		
	cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles"	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
	cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'"		
stage 1	cd \$MODEL_A_1		
	conda activate py37_tf_1.14		
	python test_stages.py --rounds=1 --batch=16 --schedule_level=3 &> out.log		
	cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles"	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
	cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"		
stage 2	cd \$MODEL_A_1		
	conda activate py37_tf_1.14		
	python test_stages.py --rounds=2 --batch=1 --schedule_level=0 &> out.log		
	cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles"	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
	cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"		

	GraphTurbo	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_stages.py --rounds=2 --batch=16 --schedule_level=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"</pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
stage 3	TVM	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_stages.py --rounds=3 --batch=1 --schedule_level=0 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"</pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
	GraphTurbo	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_stages.py --rounds=3 --batch=16 --schedule_level=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"</pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
stage 4	TVM	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_stages.py --rounds=4 --batch=1 --schedule_level=0 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"</pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$
	GraphTurbo	<pre>cd \$MODEL_A_1 conda activate py37_tf_1.14 python test_stages.py --rounds=4 --batch=16 --schedule_level=3 &> out.log cat out.log grep -A 2 "theoretical cycles" cat out.log grep "'mme_cycles'" cat out.log grep "'vme_cycles'"</pre>	$\frac{MME * 100}{mme_cycles}$	$\frac{VME * 100}{vme_cycles}$

GPU

server

The same as the NPU server.

reproduce the data

Table 4 (GPU)

```
# compile
export PATH=/usr/local/cuda/bin:$PATH
cd cutlass_vs_graphschedule
make
```

```
./test64
./test128
./test256
./test512
```